

**IMPROVING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE THROUGH LEGAL
TERMINOLOGY**

Rakhmonkulov Nozimjon Nodirjon ugli

Tashkent State Agrarian University
student of group 24-175

Samandarova Gulsara Ismatilloevna

Tashkent State Agrarian University
Teacher of Languages Department

Abstract: *The article emphasizes that in the modern world, the study of terminology is undoubtedly of great importance because terminology, on the one hand, serves as a connecting link between different fields of knowledge and, on the other hand, helps to distinguish concepts clearly.*

In connection with the rapid development and improvement of scientific and technological progress, there is a need to pay sufficient attention to legal terminology. Since the field of law does not stand still, its terminology is constantly developing and expanding its boundaries. Research in this area is carried out by lawyers, linguists, and terminologists, who are representatives of relevant fields of science and technology. Thus, legal terminology plays a vital role in improving the professional competence of legal education students in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: *legal term, terminology, professional competence, student, improvement, direction of legal education, legal documents.*

Legal terms are verbal designations of concepts that describe the content of laws and other regulatory legal acts. Words and expressions used in legislation have a clear and specific meaning and are distinguished by semantic unambiguity and external functional stability. In this regard, it is important to explain legal concepts to students in their direction and teach them their generalized names [1].

Legal terms help students clearly and correctly express legal norms to achieve maximum compactness of the legal text. Considering the limited volume of the normative text, legal terms are its basis and the foundation of its primary rules.

An essential feature of legal terms as a means of professional communication is that they are closely related to the worldview and ideology of the ruling class, various political and legal theories, scientific directions, and legal experience.

The most critical legislative document is the primary basis of legal terminology in improving students' professional competence. These documents establish terminological norms for students and serve as a reference for issuing sub-legal acts by legislative bodies.

The main legal terms of the Constitution are a source of improving students' professional competence[2,4].

For them, an essential feature of legal terminology is the systematicity and internal consistency arising from the logic of the law itself. Legal terms form a complex organic system and are interconnected in various ways. Thus, it is more accurate to explain to students the interrelationship of terms, as well as to show with examples how stable expressions reflecting similar concepts are formed from one word: the term "law" is used to create such expressions and terms as "legal relationship," "legal consciousness," "crime," and "authority." The term "lawsuit" gives rise to such terms as "plaintiff," "claim consideration," "lawsuit period," and "lawsuit application" and its characteristics: "sale"—"sale of building"; "pension"—"old" "age pension." In legislation, there are terms consisting of several independent words, such as "judiciary." It is also worth noting that the improvement of students' professional competencies consists in a deeper understanding of legal terms, the meaning of which is somewhat conditional and requires additional explanations compared to the everyday vocabulary; these

include terms such as "limitation period," "legal entity," and "real estate".

Along with the assimilation of legal terms by students, one of the distinctive features of terminology is its widespread use. Various social relations are the subject of legal regulation. There is almost no sphere of life that is not directly or indirectly influenced by law. Therefore, while studying regulatory documents, students analyze everyday vocabulary, the nomenclature of industrial products, the names of various services, and dictionaries of different fields of knowledge. The constancy of the legislative vocabulary and resistance to unreasonable linguistic innovations are necessary conditions for its stability. However, this does not mean there are no changes in the legislator's vocabulary. As a rule, most of the terms used in legislation remain unchanged and do not undergo significant changes. At the same time, some terms are not used in legislation since the relations that gave rise to them have disappeared: these are the terms "loss of rights," "peasant labour," and "sedentary lifestyle[6]."

Some terms are being replaced by other, more specific terms: "people's brigades" instead of "police assistance group," "compulsory insurance" instead of "wage insurance," etc. New terms are appearing: "prosecutor", "collateral", "housing lease", etc., and recently "collective labour dispute", "communal property", etc [3,5]. It is necessary to prove and analyze the interrelationship of legal terms, the primary material for writing legal norms, for students to master them. Using them, the state, as a symbol of its authority, speaks in the language of law and expresses its will: abolishes and changes norms, establishes new rules of behaviour, and strengthens existing social relations. With the help of legal terms, any will take the form of a constitution, current laws, government resolutions, ministerial directives and other regulatory documents. The terminology of the legal sphere differs from the terminological systems of different fields of knowledge. It should be noted that the Latin language greatly influenced the formation of legal terminology, which led to the loss of the connection between legal and general literary languages.

LIST OF REFERENCES.

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasining qarori, 27.04.2010 yildagi 71-II-son, Normativ-huquqiy atamalar komissiyasini tuzish to‘g‘risida
2. Kerimov. D.A. Legislative technique: scientific-method. and training. Manual. M.: Normainfra-M 1998.
3. Kerimov. D.A. Culture and technique of lawmaking. M.: legal literature, 1991
4. Kartashev. V.N. Legal technique, tactics, strategy and technology. N. Novgorod, 2000
5. Pokrovsky I.A. Basic problems of civil law. M.: Statut, 2013.
6. Tolstik V.A. Legal terminology. Russia, 2012